

Impacts of Ghana's Growth and Poverty Alleviation Programme II on the Livelihoods and Coping Strategies of Smallholder Farming Households: Juaben Municipality Context

Dr. Peter Kojo Boateng

Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences,
Centre for Development Studies, University of Agder,
Postboks, Kristiansand

Abstract

Ghana has a poverty reduction strategy (Ghana Poverty Reduction Strategy I, 2003-2005), and a second PRS had just completed its implementation phase in 2009. The Growth and Poverty Reduction Strategy II (GPRS II) is the focus of this study. In addition, the study provides critical perspectives on realizing the potential multiplier effects of sustainable agriculture in the promotion of sustainable rural development and selectively reviews major literature on the role of agriculture in sustainable rural development.

This study fills the void by providing a theoretically informed empirical investigation of the effects that the agricultural productivity sub-sector of the GPRS II has had on the capacity of smallholder farmers to establish long-term livelihoods. According to Sagoe (2006), adverse socio-economic conditions like negative terms of trade and inadequate agricultural infrastructure often interact with climate variability to undermine agricultural productivity and, by extension, farmers' livelihoods.

The study took an analytic-centric approach to the GPRS II policy analysis, focusing on farming communities in the Ejisu-Juaben municipality of the Ashanti region of Ghana at the micro level. Additionally, conceptual and methodological frameworks for livelihood analysis were used to evaluate the capabilities of local smallholder farmers to build livelihood resilience in the face of the GPRS II. It was uncovered that albeit a considerable lot of the mediations in the district's activity plan appeared to adjust to the most basic exact requirements of nearby ranchers for versatile vocation improvement, the GPRS II has not properly helped the more greater part of ranchers in the region, and subsequently been delayed in its neediness decrease processes. According to a livelihood resilience analysis, for instance, the majority of smallholder farmers in the municipality have not been able to adequately develop capital assets for more productivity, maintaining extremely poor and vulnerable livelihoods, despite the fact that some smallholder farmers were able to develop productive capital assets and to build viable and sustainable livelihoods through the activities of the GPRS II.

Key Word: Poverty Reduction Strategy, Livelihood Resilience, Critical Perspectives, Sustainable

Introduction

The Neediness Decrease Methodology (PRS) move toward supported by the World Bank and the Global Money related Asset lies at the focal point of advancement help, obligation alleviation, and improvement arranging in many emerging nations, including Ghana. Worldwide support of the methodology as basic for more viable neediness decrease and better improvement help is reflected in the Money related Agreement and the Rome Statement (Driscoll, 2004). Ghana has executed a PRS (Ghana Destitution Decrease Methodology I, 2003-2005) and a second era of PRS (Development and Neediness Decrease Technique II, 2006-2009) had quite recently passed its execution gradually ease in 2009. While there is plainly a component of coherence in the PRSs, the second contrasts from the primary in various ways. For example, while the main period of the public authority's procedure accentuated projects and ventures to decrease neediness, the subsequent stage centers around the execution of exercises that instigate development and can possibly uphold the making of riches.

This study will zero in on the subsequent PRS - that is the Development and Neediness Decrease Methodology II (GPRS II). In particular, it will look at the impacts of the GPRS II on the jobs and survival techniques of smallholder cultivating families in the Ejisu-Juaben district of the Ashanti Locale of Ghana. Strategies that help the livelihoods of smallholder ranchers are pivotal in endeavors to handle destitution and craving, particularly when they are intended to join various areas of public mediation. As will be made sense of additional in the review, the jobs choices accessible to individuals, in for instance rustic cultivating networks, are basic for individuals' survival techniques to foes in financial living and working circumstances. This point is chosen against the background that the essential area (horticulture, mining and quarrying, ranger service) keeps on overwhelming the Ghanaian economy, as far as its commitments to yield, work, income age, and unfamiliar trade profit. Farming is the really monetary action and, right now, represents around 51% of the Gross domestic product and around 54% of the workforce (Ghana Measurable Assistance, 2010).

By and large, the social construction remains prevalently customary, rustic, and casual

Indeed, even in the fallout of two Prs', the overall evaluation of the general results of the strategy have delivered blended results, particularly in mediations connecting with topical areas of creation and beneficial work in horticulture, with the expectation to diminish neediness. The difficulties are various. The concentrate likewise centers on survival techniques to weaknesses smallholder ranchers face in their everyday livelihoods exercises. The fundamental weakness is climatic changeability and its impacts on their occupations, as these ranchers predominantly practice downpour took care of rural frameworks. It is in many cases remarked, both in scholar and non-scholastic circles,

in Ghana that regular atmospheric conditions are turning out to be progressively flighty and capricious because of normal and human-actuated factors so that weather conditions are currently unique in relation to those that have been knowledgeable about the past and adjusted to. Frequently, fluctuation in climatic circumstances cooperates with unfriendly financial circumstances, for example, disadvantageous terms of exchange and poor horticultural framework to subvert rural efficiency and likewise, ranchers' occupations (Sagoe, 2006).

The exploration will be separated into (5) five parts. Section 1 will frame the proposition for the review. Section 2 presents a survey of important writing and the hypothetical system on which the review's examination is based. Part 3 examine exhaustively the system for this review and give legitimizations for the illustrated approach. Section 4 will contact primarily on show of experimental discoveries and information examination. At last, part 5 will examine illustrations learnt as a rundown and propose suggestions where essential. In the sections that will follow, these issues will be introduced.

As the discoveries in the stockpile side of ranchers' cooperation by the Ejisu-Juaben directorate of the Service of Food and Agribusiness MOFA has shown, despite the fact that arranging cycles and needs appraisal to recognize and carry out mediations in the activity plan included a few level of meeting and support of concerned ranchers, the cycle has predominantly been hierarchical. Contribution of ranchers in the process is very little.

Strategies for scattering data about the program are exceptionally restricted in reach

For example, large numbers of the ranchers are uneducated and simply spreading data by data vans or radio may not be enough for them to completely fathom the program and what's going on with it. There might should be two-way correspondence processes among ranchers and the MOFA for them to enough comprehend what's going on with the program. This has additionally added to the circumstance where numerous ranchers are even ignorant about civil level mediations to advance sped up development in horticultural efficiency and improvement of ranchers' vocations.

While it is conceivable to distinguish the test with the MOFA as for absence of cooperation for smallholder ranchers to structure cultivating exercises and sort out themselves to get to the mediations in the activity plans, social direction and association of smallholder ranchers need not be over-looked. In the networks, that's what discoveries show however there are customs for shared help and assembling around normal qualities, doubt and anxiety toward being taken advantage of by others in joint exercises hampers the cycles of support in aggregate bartering and responsibility for. In the mean time, the systems for cooperation and the intrinsic normal practices and customs of certified aggregate

activity and bartering affect the creation and the strength of social capital in the networks.

Result, Discussion and Finding

A survey of writing on the subject appear to uncover that the GPRS II has had blended results in concerning its targets. For example, a general cross country level examination in certain parts of the program, similar to food crop yields, may record empowering results yet miniature level results particularly in rustic regions present an alternate picture. Obviously, there was a requirement for evaluations around here to propose potential suggestions for measures that will empower comparable future undertakings and intercessions to have maintainable and expansive destitution diminishing results. That was the pre-control of this examination with regards to the Ejisu-Juaben district of Ghana.

The review embraced an analycentric way to deal with strategy examination of the GPRS II zeroing in on the small size of commonly cultivating networks in the Ejisu-Juaben district of the Ashanti locale of Ghana. Work investigation reasonable and systemic structures were likewise utilized to survey the job strength building abilities of neighborhood smallholder ranchers because of impacts of the GPRS II. Further survey of writing likewise tracked down it important to adjust social (lifestyles) aspects to the economical vocations structure as a basic variable influencing the viability of neediness decrease methodologies like the GPRS II in unambiguous settings. More or less, the point of the adjusted structure was to catch the pith and acknowledgment that admittance to resources, casual and formal freedoms, the 'foundations' which oversee ladies and men's lives at the family level contrast essentially in the review region. Fluctuation in proficiency and formal training levels, homegrown and local area obligations, social traditions were completely found to impact the effect that mediations will have on families.

Questions 1: What is the level of the smallholder ranchers' support in program exercises under the further developing farming efficiency sub-part of the GPRS II?

Given an overall circumstance of low proficiency and public strategy data utilization rates among numerous ranchers in the region, they probably won't know about compulsory necessities for participatory arrangements to be made to all partners thus it very well might be expected that MOFA could willfully welcome however many ranchers as would be prudent to think on issues. Be that as it may, this isn't true. Thus, larger part of ranchers in the different cultivating networks don't know about how agrarian efficiency choices framed in the activity plans are made and which job they can play in the process to guarantee they structure their cultivating exercises to make the most of mediations in the activity plan. In any event, for the not very many ranchers who've had a few degrees of direct meetings

with the nearby MOFA directorate, they grumble they are losing their mission to look for support potential open doors chiefly in light of the fact that in the couple of times they have partaken in some cooperation - but little - their needs and concerns have not been catered for so they see not an obvious explanation to take part.

Likewise, given restricted assets for expansion, the nearby MOFA directorate has embraced a system predicated on preparing and drawing in a framework of key ranchers in every town to diffuse horticultural methods. Under these circumstances, it is normal to choose the most excited and willing learners, as these figures are bound to be compelling augmentation specialists. In doing as such, in any case, MOFA not just escapes straightforwardly preparing the more 'loafer ranchers' (as some augmentation specialists allude to them) or battling ones, yet in addition botches the chance to find out about the requirements confronting those ranchers. As the head of the nearby MOFA office remarked to me, "we advise our staff to shift focus over to the potential, to zero in on, draw in with, and gain from, effective members and fruitful instances of their work, as opposed to harping on troublesome or obstinate issues." While this could by and large give off an impression of being a decent functional procedure, it becomes tricky in the event that it brings about field sets up efficiently getting away from sound a showdown with difficulties to their model. The last option is really the situation in the region. This over-openness to a self-chose gathering of willing members makes a counterfeit pride.

Question 2: What are the ecological and working states of the ranchers in the region? Have the ranchers encountered any change(s) in these circumstances, and if indeed, how would they adapt to these changes?

Results from essential information sources suggested that there is some type of agreement among the ranchers those climatic circumstances (precipitation design, temperature conveyance, mugginess, and so forth) that they are acclimated with in their for the most part downpour took care of cultivating exercises have changed and continue to change. This essential record additionally appears to adjust to the finishes of the logical examination concerning environment situations under the Netherlands Environmental Change Studies Help Program (NCCSAP) about falling mean yearly precipitation levels and climbing mean yearly temperature levels in the semi-deciduous woods locale of Ghana (where the Ejisu-Juaben district is situated) throughout the long term. The primary sign of environment changeability influencing ranchers in the district had to do with shakiness of and changes in anticipated climatic examples. There are other recognized significant financial elements which have huge consequences on crafted by smallholder ranchers in the region. Current situation with creation levels (counting crop yields and maker costs of harvests), land, capital, work, and acknowledge were distinguished as the primary financial marks of states of work which have critical consequences on the

efficiency of smallholder ranchers in the district. It has likewise been uncovered commonly that smallholder ranchers in the region are encountering, or have encountered, antagonistically changing patterns in costs, land, capital, work, and credit assets which influence their vocations.

Commitments of the neighborhood MOFA directorate to help smallholder ranchers adjust to and adapt to weaknesses in climatic and financial work conditions have been exceptionally negligible in that numerous ranchers have needed to depend on in some cases inadequate transformation systems, for example, moving creation periods, steady treatment of land, water gathering, among others. The examinations show that ranchers' method for work reflected boundless responsive yet not expectant ways of dealing with hardship or stress. The truth of the matter is survival methods of ranchers distinguished in the review region signified momentary responsive reactions which is frequently not compelling to moderate environment weaknesses, for example, since change is just acquainted accordingly with the beginning of the effects that will re-happen. In any case, native information acquired over the course of the years have empowered most of ranchers in the region to likewise foster some type of the fairly more powerful expectant survival techniques where they change their cultivating frameworks before the effects occur. This showed that similarly as the ranchers' jobs were in danger to weaknesses like environment changeability, those dangers additionally push the genuine qualities of the neighborhood ranchers in transformation measures.

Question 3: What is the general exhibition of the GPRS II to working on agrarian efficiency and ranchers' vocations in the review region?

The review utilized the Occupation Resource Status Following (LAST) strategic system to break down the general execution of the GPRS II on working on horticultural efficiency and creating strong jobs for smallholder ranchers in the region. The reason for the LAST strategic structure in evaluating generally influences is double; first it offers a multi-faceted view on the appraisal. Second, there is demonstrated reason that the resource - monetary, physical, human, normal, and social capital resources - status of the poor is major to understanding the choices open to them, the techniques they take on to accomplish vocations, the results they seek to and the weakness setting under which they work (Ellis, 2000).

The LAST file computations uncovered that while 38% of cultivating families were being outrageous poor before the GPRS II and preceding 2006, there was a slight decrease to 34% of cultivating families in the region being outrageous poor after the GPRS II in 2009. This implies the livelihoods of ranchers in the super unfortunate class don't have the flexibility to be extremely useful in a changing weakness setting. The level of weak families additionally declined imperceptibly from 44%

before the GPRS II to 43 percent after the GPRS

Most of families in the example are anyway still weak Here once more, it very well may be gathered that cultivating families having a place with those classes were scarcely ready to get to large numbers of the mediations of the neighborhood MOFA directorate.

There are likewise minimal increments of suitable and manageable cultivating families from 13% to 16% and 5% to 7% individually when the GPRS II. Data from this outcome suggests the way that the GPRS II has simply possibly added to the decrease of neediness and advancement of versatile occupations over the inception period to date (Walk 17 2011). This affirms discoveries and examination in past areas of the exploration as to participatory, the executives, and subsidizing issues why the GPRS II has not properly helped the more greater part of ranchers in the region, and hence been exceptionally delayed in progress made in its neediness decrease processes.

The information obtained was then used to look at the development (progress) between the four classifications framed above from 2006 to 2009 to decide the degree which, if any, the GPRS II has assisted cultivating families with traveling to better and strong vocations. To this end, cultivating families were distinguished as being 'ineffective', 'battling', 'effective' and 'best' families in view of their headings of progress on the LAST collected multi-layered markers when the GPRS II.

The outcomes showed that around 34% of cultivating families had been fruitless in creating strong livelihoods and working on their ways of life either in light of the fact that they traveled from reasonable/manageable jobs to weak livelihoods or being very poor or remained very poor when the GPRS II. Additionally, around 43% of cultivating families kept attempting to accomplish strong livelihoods and better expectations for everyday comforts, and in this manner remained being helpless. In any case, there were around 5% and 18% of cultivating families who have been somewhat 'effective' and 'best' in their tough vocations advancement endeavors separately. It ought to anyway be noticed that among the 18% of 'best' cultivating families, just 1 (one) each traveled from the outrageous neediness and weak family classifications to the reasonable vocation class. The tremendous remaining portion traveled from suitable livelihoods to maintainable jobs. This could be on the grounds that a few up until recently feasible families previously had some critical measures of useful resources which the GPRS II aided improve for guaranteeing better livelihoods.

Conclusion

However much it is admirable that 5% and 18 % of cultivating families in the district were 'fruitful' and 'best' separately, the bigger level of cultivating families still 'fruitless' (34%) and 'battling'

(43%) to become 'effective' or 'best' makes it progressively challenging to contend, overall, that the GPRS II have been carried out effectively in habits to empower until now unfortunate smallholder ranchers in the region to create feasible, economical as well as versatile occupations altogether. This amounts to discoveries and examination in past segments of the exploration as to participatory, the board, and financing issues that the GPRS II has not appropriately helped the more larger part of ranchers in the district, and consequently been extremely delayed in progress made in its destitution decrease processes.

Consequently, in view of these exact discoveries, perceptions in the field, and examinations, I reject the relational word of the review and contend that the GPRS II has not been utilized as a mediation to successfully foster fundamental load of capital resources (human, physical, monetary, normal, and social) essential for unfortunate smallholder cultivating families to foster sufficiently strong and economical jobs.

Reference

- Aduwum, R.O (2006) The Growth and Poverty Reduction Strategy – GPRS II (2006 – 2009), National Development Planning Commission, Accra
- Altieri, M. (1989), “Agroecology: A New Research and Development Paradigm for World Agriculture”, Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment, 27, pp.37-46
- Aryeetey, E. (2007) Globalisation, Employment, and Poverty in Ghana, Institute of Statistical, Social, and Economic Research, University of Ghana, Legon
- Ashley, C. and Maxwell, S. (2001) “Rethinking Rural Development”, Development Policy Review, 19(4):395 – 425
- Brundtland, H. (1987) Our Common Future, Oxford University Press, Oxford, for the World Commission on Environment and Development
- Burton, I., Huq, S., Lim, B., Pilifosova, O., and Schipper, E.L. (2002) “From Impacts Assessment to Adaptation Priorities: The Shaping of Adaptation Policy”, Climate Policy, Vol. 2, p. 145-159.
- Cahn, M. (2002) The Business of Living: Rural Micro-Enterprise and Sustainable Livelihoods. PhD thesis submitted to Massey University, Palmerston North.
- Datt, G. and Ravallion, M. (1996) “How Important to India’s Poor is the Sectoral Composition of Economic Growth”? World Bank Economic Review, 10(1): 1 – 25
- Diskin, P. (1997) Agricultural Productivity Indicators Measurement Guide, Food and Nutrition Technical Assistance, Academy of Educational Development, Washington DC, USA
- Evans, P. (1996) “Government Action, Social Capital and Development: Reviewing the Evidence on Synergy”, World Development, Vol. 24, No. 6, pp. 1119-1132
- Foster, A.D and Rosenzweig, M.R (2004) “Agricultural Productivity Growth, Rural Economic

Diversity, and Economic Reforms: India, 1970 – 2000”, Quarterly Journal of Economics, University of Chicago, 0013-0079/2004/5203-0002

- Galasso, E. and Ravallion, M. (2000) Social Organisations and Project Performance: Evidence from Bangladesh, The World Bank, Washington DC
- Ghana Cocoa Board (COCOBOD) (1998) Socio-Economic Study Final Report, Cocoa Board, Ghana; MASDAR. 232p
- Grindle, M. (1996) Challenging the State: Crisis and Innovation in Latin America and Africa, Cambridge University Press, New York
- Hooper, A. and James, K. (1994) “Sustainability and Pacific Cultures”, Pacific Islands Development Series No 1, East-West Center Working Papers, Hawaii
- IPCC (2007) Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Summary for Policy Makers
- IUCN, UNEP, and WWF (1991), Caring for the Earth: A Strategy for Sustainable Living, Gland, Switzerland: IUCN, UNEP, WWF
- Keppo, I., O’Neil, C., and Riahl, K. (2007) “Probabilistic Temperature Change Projections and Energy System Implications of Greenhouse Gas Emission Scenarios”, Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Volume 74, Issue 7, Pages 936-961
- Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MoFA) (2009) Food and Agriculture Sector Development Policy (FASDEP II), Republic of Ghana
- Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development (2006) A Repository of all Districts in Ghana; Ejisu-Juaben District
- Mosse, D. (2006) “Anti-Social Anthropology? Objectivity, Objection, and the Ethnography of Public Policy and Professional Communities”, Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute, 12(4): 935-956
- Müller, C., Cramer, W., Hare, W.L. and Lotze-Campen, H. (2011) Climate Change Risks for African Agriculture, Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America, Vol. 108, No. 11, 4313 – 4315
- National Development Planning Commission (2006) Guidelines for the Preparation of District Medium-Term Development Plan Under the Growth and Poverty Reduction Strategy, Accra, Ghana
- National Development Planning Commission (2009) The Implementation of the Growth and Poverty Reduction Strategy 2006-2009: 2008 Annual Progress Report, Accra, September 2009
- Scoones, I. (1998) “Sustainable Rural Livelihoods. A Framework for Analysis”, IDS Working Paper No. 72. IDS, Brighton
- Schneider, H. (1999) Participatory Governance: The Missing Link for Poverty Reduction, Policy Brief No 17. OECD Development Centre: Paris
- Walcott, J. (2004) Agriculture and Biodiversity: Connections for Sustainable Development. Bureau of Rural Sciences, Canberra

- Webersik, C., and Wilson, C. (2009) “Achieving Environmental Sustainability and Growth in Africa: The Role of Science, Technology, and Innovation”, Sustainable Development, Volume 17, Issue 6, pages 400-413
- Wolter, D. (2008) Ghana: Agriculture is Becoming a Business, Business for Development: Promoting Commercial Agriculture in Africa, Development Centre, OECD.
- World Bank (2007) Ghana: Joint Staff Assessment of the Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper Annual Progress Report, July 2007, IMF Country Report No. 07/208